

**ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG
UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE IFE,
NIGERIA**

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) thesis entitled: “entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Nigeria” was conducted by Olaoye Timilehin Samuel, in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) degree in Sociology and Anthropology, in the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship is considered as a source of income and invariably a means to reduce the poverty rate therefore the prevalence of entrepreneurship among youths in Nigeria is on a high rate and there are several factors responsible for such development; for instance, in Nigeria, unemployment is on a high rate in that there are high numbers of graduates from various institutions in Nigeria. This paper provides findings on the factors that determine entrepreneurial engagement, effects of entrepreneurial engagement on academics, types of entrepreneurial and programmes made available to encourage entrepreneurial engagement among undergraduate students using Obafemi Awolowo University as a case study. Empirical results on whether engagement in entrepreneurial activities interferes with academic performance; extent of involvement and gender differences are also presented. Descriptive statistics was employed in analysing the results of the study findings. The results revealed that family support and business background in business, students' desire to own a business and anxiety about their ability to find and maintain employment in Nigeria significantly predict students' interest in entrepreneurship. Engagement in entrepreneurial activity has no significant effect on students' academic performance. The findings revealed that students' experiences as entrepreneurs have affected their career prospects positively that is most students were likely to become self-employed and entrepreneurs after graduation.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, academic performance and undergraduate students

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the Study

Entrepreneurship entails perceiving and identifying business opportunities, deciding on a business site, innovating a creative solution to an opportunity, taking on all uninsurable risks, and managing an ongoing organization (Egboh, 2009). State of Entrepreneurship in Nigeria 2021, has shown that 43 and 67 per cents of entrepreneurs in the country are women and youths whose brackets fall within 18 and 35 years respectively. It further showed that 60 per cent of entrepreneurs in Nigeria attended tertiary education and has at least a university bachelor's degree or Higher National Diploma (HND) from polytechnics (Onwuamaeze, 2021).

The prevalence of entrepreneurship among youths in Nigeria is on a high rate and there are several factors responsible for such development; for instance, in Nigeria, unemployment is on a high rate in that there are high numbers of graduates from various institutions in Nigeria. Also, the high level of poverty in Nigeria has increased the interest of youths in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is considered as a source of income and invariably a means to reduce the poverty rate. In 2022, the unemployment rate in Nigeria is estimated to reach 33 per cent. This figure was projected to be 32.5 per cent in 2021. Chronological data show the unemployment rate in Nigeria has risen constantly in the past years. In the fourth quarter of 2020, over 33 per cent of the labour force was unemployed (Doris, 2022). Youth unemployment rate in Nigeria increased to 53.40 per cent in the fourth quarter of 2020 from 40.80 per cent in the second quarter of 2020 (The Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). In 2020, 40 per cent or 83 million Nigerians live in poverty. Although Nigeria's poverty profile for 2021 has not yet been released, it is estimated that the

number of poor people will increase to 90 million or 45 per cent of the population in 2022 (The Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

The best way to combat youth unemployment, underemployment, and poverty is through entrepreneurship, especially when educated people are having trouble finding work (Brownhilder, 2014). There are macro and micro factors that affect people's interests in entrepreneurship in Nigeria. The macro factors are unemployment and poverty. These are factors that affect the wider society interests in entrepreneurship. There are also micro factors which are attitude, subject norm, perceived behavioural control, gender, age, ethnicity, family background, income(allowances) and course of study that affect individuals.

In Nigeria, academic performance among students is prioritized; for instance, the Western part of Nigeria where this study was conducted values academic performance among students. In the history of Nigeria, Chief Obafemi Awolowo, Premier of the Western Region, gave so much attention to academic performance to the extent that he pioneered free education in the Western part of Nigeria. It is important to point those other parts of Nigeria also value education but emphasis is on the Western part of Nigeria because it is the location where this study was conducted. Nigeria had produced great people with great academic performance that had changed the global world positively; for instance, people like Wole Soyinka, Akinsola Akinwowo and many more.

In Obafemi Awolowo University, academic performance is prioritized. The motto of the school "For learning and culture" depicts that the school management places so much value on academic performance. The school management's emphasis on academic performance reflected in the students' attitude toward academic activities that are necessary for their academic performance and also influence their attitudes toward entrepreneurship on campus. This study examined the

factors that influence students' engagement in entrepreneurial activity and whether such involvement has any effect on academic performance among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife.

1.2. Statement of the research problem

Previous studies such as (Brownhilder, 2014; Khuong & An, 2016; Ayegba & Omale, 2016; Malebana, 2014) have mainly focused on the determinants of entrepreneurial intention with less attention to actual engagement in entrepreneurship. Studies such as (Osakede, Lawanson & Sobawale, 2017; Agetue & Nnamdi, 2014; Tumbali, 2019) have mainly focused on examining the determinants of entrepreneurial engagement among undergraduate students and whether such activity has any effect on academic performance.

There was, therefore a need to consult several literatures in order to fill gap in research. This study was able to advance knowledge in research in that several studies have researched on several locations except Obafemi Awolowo University and also the time those studies were conducted was not recent as the case may be. This study was interested in providing insight to other determinants of entrepreneurship engagement among undergraduate students such as ethnicity, course of study, income of students and many others that was be identified in the course of the study. This study was also interested into the types of entrepreneurship activities among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University which other studies have not sufficiently considered.

1.3. Research Questions

This study sought to address these following questions:

- i. What are the possible determinants of entrepreneurship engagement among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria?
- ii. What are the effects of entrepreneurship engagement among the undergraduate students?
- iii. What are the types of entrepreneurship engagement among the undergraduate students?
- iv. What are the programmes/platforms made available to encourage the undergraduate students to engage in entrepreneurship on campus?

1.4. Research Objectives

The main objective of this study was to understand the relationship between entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. This study sought to achieve these following specific objectives which are:

- i. Identify the determinants of entrepreneurship engagement among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the effects of entrepreneurship engagement among undergraduate students.
- iii. Identify the types of entrepreneurship engagement among the undergraduate students; and
- iv. Investigate programmes/platforms available to encourage undergraduate students to engage in entrepreneurship on campus.

1.5. Significance of the Study

This study sought to contribute to the body of knowledge on other determinants of entrepreneurship engagement among undergraduate students and also provided the university and other various universities in Nigeria with orientation to provide schemes, programmes and platforms to encourage entrepreneurship among students since entrepreneurship was seen as a means to alleviate poverty and reduce the problem of unemployment among graduates and Nigeria

at large. This study filled gap in research in space; that is, location of study and time in which the study was conducted. This study sought to educate the wider society and entrepreneurs especially students about the relationship between entrepreneurship engagement and academic performance among undergraduate students.

1.6. Scope of the Study

This study was interested in investigating the relationship between entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University. In this study, student entrepreneurs of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun state, Nigeria were used.

1.7. Definition of Concepts

Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurship entails perceiving and identifying business opportunities, deciding on a business site, innovating a creative solution to an opportunity, taking on all uninsurable risks, and managing an ongoing organization.

Academic Performance: Academic performance is a student's quantifiable and observable behaviour across time.

Undergraduate students: These are students that are in Obafemi Awolowo University for their Bachelor degree.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

In social research, the place of existing academic literature in research cannot be overemphasised as there is a need for present study to be informed by existing works in order to contribute new knowledge or validate existing knowledge in the scientific community.

Against this background, this chapter presented the review of existing literature such as academic papers, journal articles, conference periodical, books, newspapers and other forms of records related to the problem under discourse in this study. This section was based on a critical review of existing literature related to entrepreneurship and academic performance in order to lay the template upon which the findings of this research undertaking was premised.

This chapter employed the thematic style of literature review. This chapter comprised three categories and which were conceptual review; where scholarly definitions of the concepts of entrepreneurship and academic performance was critically reviewed; theoretical review, where relevant theories to the topic under discourse was critically reviewed; and empirical review, where empirical works and reports was reviewed.

2.1. Conceptual Review

This section covered key concepts of this study and history of the concepts.

2.1.1. Definitions and Concepts of Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneur is defined and described by different authors and entrepreneurs in different ways. However, there is no general definition of an entrepreneur but all the definitions have common indices. Since the 16th and 17th centuries, the term "entrepreneur" has been used. The word

"entrepreneur" comes from the French word "entreprendre," which means "to take on." According to French legal and economic literature, an entrepreneur is a person who is active and gets things done (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2001). An entrepreneur spots a gap in the market that no one else is filling and develops a solution (Freedman, 2021). According to Cantillon, an entrepreneur is a person who buys production equipment at a specific price in order to combine it into a product that he will sell at an unknown price at the time he commits to his costs.

According to Meredith (1983), an entrepreneur is someone who can detect and analyse business opportunities, put together the resources needed to take advantage of them, and take the necessary steps to succeed. Unachukwu (1992) defines an entrepreneur as a person (or group of people) who starts a firm, organises, controls, and merges other forces of production, supervises the production processes, and bears all the risks that come with it.

Soyibo (2006) defines entrepreneurship as the process of recognising a need-satisfying opportunity and turning it into a valuable product or service. It can also refer to the process and activities that entrepreneurs engage in in order to capture the value associated with business possibilities.

According to Schumpeter (2002), an entrepreneur is a person who creates new combinations of means of production that cause disequilibrium. He went on to say that the entrepreneurs are the essential players in development since they are a highly motivated and skilled group of people. They anticipate a potentially profitable opportunity and attempt to capitalize on it. Entrepreneur, he claims, is essentially an innovator, and an innovator is someone who creates new combinations.

The definitions above illustrate that an entrepreneur is a creative individual who is willing to take on all of the risks that come with owning a business. He organises work, makes final decisions, finds clients to assure the company's survival, and manages a variety of other tasks at the same

time. In simple terms, an entrepreneur is a person who recognises business possibilities, starts a business, and manages scarce resources wisely and efficiently to ensure the business venture's profitability and longevity.

A general definition of entrepreneurship could be very difficult as it has attracted a great deal of attention from different authors and organisation within the global community because of its contribution to the country's economic growth and development and solution to the problem of high unemployment rate and poverty rate. Even with the different definitions given by authors and organisations, there were common indices that were notable in different definitions which include risk taking, creation of wealth, production of services that satisfy customers' needs, perceiving and taking advantage of opportunities, innovation and creativity and others.

In the works reviewed, different definitions of entrepreneurship were analysed. Entrepreneurship had been defined as the persistent pursuit of opportunities to amass wealth through the innovative creation of a product or service that meets customers' needs, while using limited resources in a way that results in an enterprise's growth that meets the expectations of stakeholders whose roles sustain the business (Adidu & Olannye, 2006). According to Nwaogwugwu and Ugiagbe (2008), explain that entrepreneurship is defined as an individual's or group's willingness and aptitude to seek out investment possibilities, particularly through invention, develop, and successfully run a business.

Entrepreneurship entails perceiving and identifying business opportunities, deciding on a business site, innovating a creative solution to an opportunity, taking on all uninsurable risks, and managing an ongoing organization (Egboh, 2009). This definition given is more suitable due to its emphasis on some tenets of entrepreneurship, which include perception of business opportunities, innovation, creativity and risk taking. However, this definition is criticized for combining

creativity and risk taking. Further, Agetue and Nnamdi (2017), define entrepreneurship as the process of recognising a business opportunity, mobilising resources, and taking action(s) under the umbrella of a company that is marked by risk-taking, innovation, and creativity in order to address the needs of individuals, organisations, or society.

Entrepreneurship is defined as the ability of an individual with a certain amount of capital to initiate, innovate, make decisions, and be responsible enough to take risks in economic activities (Cadaru & Badulescu, 2015). Shane and Venkataraman (2000) define entrepreneurship as a "nexus" that entails enterprising persons grasping and utilising attractive opportunities. In the early phases of starting a business, entrepreneurs frequently have to do more with and use the abilities and resources they have during the planning and launch process, utilising the resources they have at their disposal with the least amount of money and the most amount of capital improvisation and cleverness (Harrison, 2004; Miner, 2001).

According to Hessels and Naude (2017), a broader definition of entrepreneurship as the resources, process and state of being through which individuals with ability and agency utilize positive opportunities in the market for generating individual and/or social value. Havinal (2009), defines entrepreneurship by relating it to what an entrepreneur does; entrepreneurship involves creation of something new, organising production and undertaking risks and handling economic uncertainty involved in enterprise.

From the various definitions given, it is expedient to note that the works of literature presented various definitions but there are still common variables in each definition. Entrepreneurship is associated with several operations such as risk taking, identifying investment opportunities, deciding the opportunity to work extremely hard on how to promote and set up the business

enterprise, gathering the scarce resources required for production and distribution, and organising and managing human and material resources to meet the set goal (Echezona & Monday, 2011).

2.1.2. History of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship activity existed as far back as in the 17th century and the original entrepreneurs were traders and merchants. The first recorded trading act was in New Guinea around 17000 BCE when people exchanged a volcanic glass (Obsidian) for food, skins, tools and other needed items. Apparently, it continued for a long time where people from different tribes exchanged properties with other tribes. According Ani (1999), entrepreneurship began when people produced more products than they required, forcing them to trade surpluses.

Agriculture was the first business venture that individuals took on. Farmers began commercial farming, and non-farmers specialised in other companies, as people involved in food production and other businesses. Then came barter trading, when individuals would sell animals for farm products among themselves, and the scope of trading began to broaden. Afterwards, they became specialized in fishing, clothes- making, hunting, tool-making. These were entrepreneurial activities and the people were one of the earliest entrepreneurs in human civilization. Around 15000 BCE, the first animal domestication began taking place, and around 10,000 BCE, the first domestication of plants.

Early entrepreneurship started with trade by barter before the advent of any form of money. Trade by barter existed for a long time but ended when nations started experiencing a ‘coincidence of wants. People were getting irrelevant things in exchange for their products, and since they were trading across boundaries returns could not be monitored. The existence of coincidence of wants limited trade and in the process of finding solutions, money was invented.

The advent of money led to the use of different objects as currency. The earliest form was the shekel in 3000 BCE. The shekel is the unit of weight and currency. It was a specific weight of barley and equivalent amounts of silver, bronze, copper and many more. Later on, Central Asia started using silver bars. Ancient Asia, Africa and India used cowrie shells. Some countries made use of tobacco leaves, son beads and other sticks and rocks. Afterwards, coinage evolved, then paper money. The existence of currency makes it easy to trade across borders and trading boomed.

2.1.3. Entrepreneurship in Nigeria

In Nigeria, entrepreneurship started when the goods produced by her citizens exceeded their needs. They exchanged surplus items for what they needed. For instance, farmers started selling out his farm produce in exchange for animal product from hunters. Farmers started selling their farm produce and engaged services of their family members for greater output. While others were farming, others became specialised in other activities like craft work. These entrepreneurial activities contributed positively to Nigerian economy until the colonial era.

Prior to the colonial era, Nigeria started direct trade with the Europeans. The Europeans built coastal bases around the seas in parts of Nigeria, started slave trading and bought slaves from Nigeria. Afterwards, the slave trade business experienced boom and Nigerians kings or rulers also participated.

The colonial era influenced the Nigerian system of trading and attitude to entrepreneurship activities in that Africans were trained and employed as low rank offices in the local administrations. The education that was promoting inequality and the colonial masters were amassing wealth of Nigeria. During this period, the educational curriculum that was introduced by the colonial masters did not have regard for entrepreneurship. The educational curriculum

concentrated more on arithmetic, logic, religion, reading and writing which were all about book and religion. This greatly affected the entrepreneurial culture striving among Nigerians tended toward white collar jobs as a means of livelihood.

After independence of Nigeria on October 1 1960, Nigerians government become aware of the menace the colonial educational system has caused on entrepreneurship and economic growth and the awareness became the turning point in the history of entrepreneurship in Nigeria. There have several attempts to reverse it and the solution was to make education a tool for national development. In order to achieve this, the government established organization like: National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Nigeria Industrial Development Bank (NIDB), Entrepreneurship Development Centre (EDC), National Open Apprenticeship Scheme (NAOS) and many more. Also, there were fund raising institutions created which include Peoples Bank of Nigeria, Funds for Small- Scale Industries (FUSSI), Do- operative societies.

In order to create an educational system to encourage entrepreneurship, the 1977 National Policy on Education was formulated. It was formulated for several purposes. One was to address the situation of entrepreneurial learning in the educational system. This policy was formulated in 1977 and revised in 1981, 1988, 2004, 2007 and 2011.

2.1.4. Concept of Academic Performance

Academic performance is pivotal in determining the human capital development of a national economy (Abaidoo, 2018). It allows students and parents to be aware of the current state of students' academic and it is relevant in determining the failure and success of an academic institution (Narad & Abdullah, 2016).

In the literature, several scholars have defined and described academic performance. According to Narad and Abdullah (2016), academic performance is the knowledge acquired and measured by a lecturer's grades as well as/or educational goals set by students and lecturers to be attained over a predetermined period of time. They continued by saying that the results of tests or ongoing assessments serve as a gauge for these aims. Academic performance is also a measure of education success, (Annie, Howard, & Midred cited in Arhad, Zaidi, & Mahmood, 2015). They stated that academic performance illustrates and evaluates how well a university, lecturers, and students have accomplished their educational goals.

According to Yusuf, Onifade, and Bello (2016), academic performance is a student's quantifiable and observable behaviour across time. He added that it is made up of a student's results on tests and assignments in such class exercises, tests, mock examinations, midterm examinations, and final examination. Martha (2009) noted that a student's academic performance is characterized by their performance in an examination, tests, and course work.

The definitions provided by the authors show how measurable results like assignments, tests, and examination scores determine academic performance.

2.2. Theoretical Review

This section projected theories that guided this study and these were; Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Event Theory.

In social research, the place of theories cannot be overemphasised because theories are essential to commence a study so also a study could facilitate the emergence of a theory in research. Theories are basically for the purpose of giving direction to a study and serve as a framework for driving the study from the point of conception to the point of conclusion. From the existing academic

literature reviewed on the relationship between entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students, there were different theories employed to serve as a framework to guide the study. This subsection delved into the review of the theories used by existing academic literature with the interest to understand the relationship between entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students.

2.2.1. Human Capital Theory

Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz, two economists in 1964, argued that education and training were investments that might boost productivity. The opportunity cost of going to university decreased as the globe collected more physical capital. Education has become a more significant part of the workforce. Human capital theory states that more education and skill training can boost a person's productive capability (Ross, 2022).

It emphasises the importance of education in improving a person's productive capacity and self-efficacy by improving their reasoning skills. In this context, entrepreneurial human capital is defined as an individual's entrepreneurial skills and dispositions. Entrepreneurial skills include recognizing opportunities, assessing viability, and coming up with new ideas and talents in problem-solving, whereas entrepreneurial dispositions refer to the individual's autonomy, risk, work, and income (Douglas & Shepherd 2005). In the context of this theory, students will have interest in entrepreneur because of their entrepreneurial skills and dispositions.

This theory had been criticized as being flawed, overly simplistic and for comparing labour with capital. It had been criticized because human capital does necessarily raise productivity. In 1976, an economist from Harvard, Richard Freeman, argued human capital only acted as indicator about talent and ability; real productivity came later through training, motivation and capital equipment

(Ross, 2022). It could also be criticized for over emphasising education without consideration of the opportunity available to all. However, this theory has given the insight into why students have interest in entrepreneurship activity because of their entrepreneurial skills and attitude.

2.2.2. Entrepreneurial Event Theory

Shapero and Sokol (1982), developed the Entrepreneurial Event model to define the interaction of cultural and social elements that can lead to the formation of a corporation by influencing individual perspectives. In this way, the model views entrepreneurship as an alternative or available choice that arises as a result of a shift in the environment. This model describes two basic kinds of perception; Perceived Desirability (PD) is the result of an individual's perceptions of entrepreneurship's desirability as it relates to their personal attitudes, values, and sentiments. The Perceived Feasibility (PF) is a measure of an individual's perceived capacity to carry out various behaviours based on their impression of available resources. The personal inclination to act on one's decisions, reflecting volitional characteristics of intentions, is known as the Propensity to Act (PTA) (Riverola & Giones, 2012). This model has also been applied to analysing entrepreneur actions on multiple occasions (Walstad & Kourilsky 1998; Peterman & Kennedy 2003). The findings confirm the model as a reliable tool for assessing entrepreneurship intent.

This theory explained how entrepreneurial intentions play role in determining entrepreneurship engagement among students. This theory pointed out students perceiving entrepreneurship as an alternative choice and was depicted by their interest in performing that behaviour in order to achieve the goal. It acts as a motivational factor that transforms attitude into entrepreneurial intention, how students' potentials influence their entrepreneurship intent and the willingness of students to engage in entrepreneurship activities.

However, this theory could be criticized for too much emphasis on cultural and social factors that can affect students' interest in entrepreneurship but failed to consider micro factors such as attitude, subject norm, perceived behavioural control, gender, age, ethnicity, family background, income and course of study that affect students' interest in entrepreneurship.

2.2.3. Production Function Approach

The origins of this model may be traced back to economics. A.R.J. Turgot invented it in 1767, but it was not well known until Charles W. Cobb and Paul Douglas utilised it in their study in 1928 (Tangaraju, Chee, Koon, Yi & Mann, 2013). This model, according to Gordon (2007), is based on the input-output principle. This is the process of converting raw resources (inputs) into finished goods and services (output).

Several scholars have utilised this approach to evaluate factors that influence academic performance. According to Martha (2010), the output factor is the students' academic performance or performance, whereas the input components are the independent variables. Tangaraju (2013) identified teaching and learning materials, lecturer quality, and family factors as common input factors.

In this study, the output factor is academic performance of a student and students' interest, regular studying, class attendance, self-motivation, attitude toward learning, lecturer's experience, syllabus completion, doing assignment, parents' involvement, provision of instructional materials, discipline, effective teaching, class size and the university environment, parents' level of education, age and gender of a student are all input factors in this study.

2.3. Empirical Review

This section covered studies that address factors affecting academic performance, functions of entrepreneurship in economic growth and development, determinant of entrepreneurial activities and summary and gaps in literature.

2.3.1. Factors Affecting Students' Academic Performance

Several studies had been undertaken in various nations to determine the elements that influence students' academic success at various levels. Farooq and Berhanu (2011) found that a student's socioeconomic status and parents' educational level in Pakistan had a substantial impact on how well they perform academically in Mathematics and English language. According to a study done in Singapore by Jayanthi, Balakrishnan, Ching, Latiff, and Nasirudeen (2014), a student's academic performance is influenced by his or her desire in pursuing a subject, co-curricular activities, nationality, and gender. Furthermore, Sibanda, Iwu, and Olumide (2015) discovered that regular study, punctuality in university, and self-motivation are the most important determinants of students' academic performance in South Africa. According to Ali, Munir, Khan, and Ahmed, daily study time, parents' socioeconomic status, and age all have a significant effect on academic performance (2013).

Furthermore, Catherine (2015) discovered that the socioeconomic position of parents, particularly those with high incomes, had a substantial impact on pupils' academic performance in Kenya's Kitale Municipality. Positive classroom climate has also been shown to have an impact on academic performance (MolokoMphale & Mhlauli, 2014). According to Maganga (2016), Nghambi (2014), and Osei-Mensah (2012), the location in which a university is located, lecturer

competency, and the availability of teaching and learning materials all have an effect on students' academic performance.

According to the discussion above, a range of factors, including but not limited to: parents' educational level, socioeconomic status, interest in a subject, gender, consistent study habits, punctuality in class, self-motivation, availability of teaching and learning materials, lecturer competency, university environment, personal goals, and personality traits, influence students' academic performance. The four categories of these factors are student, lecturer, university, and parents.

2.3.1.1. Students' Factors Affecting Academic Performance

The explanation above makes it quite evident that students had a significant impact on their academic performance. Developing an interest in a subject, participating in extracurricular activities, regular study habits, self-motivation, punctuality in university, as well as individual goals and personality traits all have an impact on students' academic performance (Sibanda 2015; Javanthi 2014; Khan and Ahmed, 2013, Ulate & Carballo, 2011).

According to Maric and Sakac (2014), students' internal and societal influences that affect their academic achievement can be divided into two categories. Internal elements that influence students' academic performance include interest in a subject's substance, internal pleasure, and aspiration, according to the researchers. Gaining social recognition and financial success were also social elements. MeenuDev (2016) discovered that a student's aptitude for a subject affects how well they succeed. Similar to this, Kpolovie, Joe, and Okoto (2014) asserted that a student's drive for studying and attitude toward university both affect their academic performance.

Additionally, according to Komakech (2015), there is a connection between students' academic performance and their university enrollment. When examining the effect of attendance on academic performance in Nigeria using a correlational technique, Oghuvbu (2017) came to the same conclusion as Komakeck. He discovered that class attendance and academic performance have a positive relationship. Stanca (2010) discovered that attendance in class had a statistically significant effect on academic performance. Several more studies have discovered the similar link (Lukkarinnen, Koivukangas, Seppala, 2016; Aden, Yahye, Dahir, 2013; Duran-Narucki, 2008).

Students' attitudes toward their studies have been found to have a significant impact on academic performance. Awang, Ahmad, Bakar, Ghani, Yunus et al. (2013) discovered a statistically significant relationship between students' attitudes toward learning and academic performance. According to Janssen and O'Brien (2014), students' learning has an indirect impact on academic performance. Regardless of their findings, Manoah, Indoshi, and Othuon (2011) verified that students' attitudes toward Mathematics had a direct impact on their academic performance. However, Uok and Langat (2015) discovered that students' attitudes toward Mathematics had no bearing on their Mathematics scores.

Afzal, Ali, Khan, and Hamid (2010) asserted that a student's own drive greatly affected how well they succeeded in school. According to the study, both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation had a positive effect on students' academic performance. They continued by stating that intrinsic motivation rather than extrinsic incentive was a stronger indicator of academic performance. In a similar vein, Haider, Quereshi, Pirzada, and Shahzadi (2015) discovered that a student's academic performance depended heavily on motivation. In their study, they found that drive, both intrinsic and extrinsic, had a statistically significant relationship with academic performance. According to

the study, students' driving characteristics, such as self-exploration, altruism, and career emphasis, as well as how they handled social pressure, had a positive effect on their academic performance.

Kusurkar, Cate, Vos, and Croiset (2013) classified motivation into Random Autonomous Motivation (RAM), Controlled Motivation (CM), and Autonomous Motivation (AM) using structural equation modelling analysis to analyse the effect of motivation on performance (AM). They discovered that internal motivation, which they defined as RAM, is strongly connected with academic performance. Furthermore, Amrai, Motlagh, Zalani, and Parhon (2011) claimed that a variety of motivational factors influenced students' academic performance.

Students' elements that influenced their academic performance were a combination of numerous indications, according to the existing literature studied. The primary characteristics that determined a student's academic performance are their interest in a subject, regular studying, class attendance, self-motivation, and attitude toward learning, according to this review. With the exception of Uok and Langat (2015), who showed a positive association between these characteristics and academic performance, all of the literature reviewed. This means that, all other things being equal, if a student had a favourable attitude about these elements, his or her academic performance would improve.

2.3.1.2. Lecturers' Factors Affecting Students' Academic Performance

Lecturers play a critical impact in students' academic success. lecturers' experience, age, gender, and professional qualification had no statistically significant link with students' academic performance, according to a study conducted by Kimani, Kara, and Njagi (2013) in Kenya on lecturer characteristics influencing academic accomplishment. They did discover, however, that performance targets, syllabus completion, paying attention to weak students, assignments, student

feedback, and a lecturer's instructional workload all had a substantial impact on students' academic performance. Akiri and Ugborugbo (2009) discovered no statistical correlation between lecturer effectiveness and academic success in Nigeria.

According to Ganyaupfu (2013), a mix of lecturer and student-centred methods had a favourable impact on academic performance. They came to the conclusion that a student-centred strategy was more effective than a lecturer-centred approach. Lecturer experience and professional training, according to Musili (2015), have a considerable impact on students' performance. Blazar (2016) confirmed that lecturers had a significant impact on their students' academic performance. However, it should be noted that little was known about the exact lecturer variables that influenced students' academic performance.

Akinsolu (2010) also found that the lecturer-student ratio, as well as the lecturer's experience and qualification, had a substantial impact on academic performance. Similarly, Ewetan & Ewetan (2015) asserted that a lecturer's level of expertise had a considerable impact on academic success in both English and mathematics. They claimed that universities with lecturers with more than ten years of experience outperform those with less than ten years of expertise.

Lecturers' teaching experience, syllabus completion, paying attention to weak students, assignments, students' evaluation, lecturer effectiveness, lecturer and student-centred method of teaching, professional training, lecturer to student ratio, and lecturer qualification were all factors that had a significant impact on students' academic performance. It was also discovered that the age and gender of the lecturer have no bearing on the academic performance of the students.

2.3.1.3. Parents Factors Affecting Students' Academic Performance

Recent studies had found that parents' involvement benefits their children's academic performance. For instance, McNeal (2014) found that parental participation affected students' behaviour and attitudes directly, but indirectly affected their academic performance. According to Chowa, Masa, and Tucker (2013), parental involvement in a student's academic performance in Ghana could be split into two types: involvement at home and involvement at a university. Their study discovered a favourable correlation between parental involvement at home and students' academic performance, but a negative correlation between parental involvement at universities and academic performance. Similarly, Mante, Awereh, and Kumea (2014) discovered that parental involvement affected their children's academic performance, albeit they did not specify which way the impact was going.

Mwirichia (2013), also noted that parental involvement in a student's academic performance took several forms. He discovered that parents participate in educational activities at university, communicated with their student's lecturers, and participate in academic activities at home. The study found that parents' involvement in home academic activities had a direct impact on their student's academic performance; parents' involvement in university academic activities had an indirect impact on academic performance; and parent-university communication did not appear to be a strong predictor of academic performance. Parents should arrange home-university tutorials for their children and establish guidelines to manage their children's study behaviour in the house, according to the study. Caro (2011) found that parents' interactions with universities had a positive effect on their children's education.

According to Matinez (2015), students who had a high level of parental involvement in their academics score much better than students who did not have any parental involvement in English

Language Arts and Mathematics. Using a multiple mediational approach, Topor, Keane, Shelton, and Calkins (2010) found a statistically significant correlation between parental involvement and ward academic performance. In Pakistan, Rafiq, Fatima, Sohail, Saleem, and Khan (2013) discovered the same outcomes. They emphasised the value of family support in assisting children with their academic performance. Mutodi and Ngirande (2014) found that academic performance in South Africa was correlated with parent-lecturer communication, family and home support, as well as well as parenting.

The researchers came to the conclusion that the most significant predictor of academic performance was family and home support. Although the level and amount of parental involvement vary, this had an indirect impact on their children's academic performance. It had been demonstrated that parental engagement has a significant positive impact on their student's academic performance.

2.3.1.4. Parents Educational Level and Students' Academic Performance

According to Khan, Iqbal, and Tasneem (2015), parents with a higher degree of education were more concerned about their children's academic performance. They discovered that the amount of education of parents had a positive impact on their children's academic performance. Muthoni (2013) discovered the same finding in Kenya. She discovered that in Kenyan secondary universities, a student's parent's degree of education was favourably associated to his or her child's performance. Similarly, Ogbugo-Ololube (2016) discovered a positive association between parental education and academic performance. Muruwei (2011) stated that, while parental education had an impact on academic performance, it was not the most important element. There were other key aspects that influenced academic performance, such as the learning environment

and facilities. Amuda and Ali (2016), on the other hand, discovered that a parent's level of education had no statistical impact on their children's academic success.

The impact of a parent's educational degree on their children's academic success appeared to be inconclusive. While some research indicated a substantial positive association, others believe that it was not the main determinant of academic performance. Furthermore, research have discovered that there is no statistically significant association between a parent's educational degree and their child's academic success. As a result, there was a gap in the literature, which the researcher tried to fill.

2.3.1.5. Student's Gender and Academic Performance

There had been a lot of research examining the connection between gender and academic performance during the last ten years (Eitle, 2005 as cited in Farooq & Berhanu, 2011). Ghazvini and Khajehpour claim that boys and girls had different cognitive abilities (2011). They found that learning tasks for girls were more flexible than those for boys.

There was a statistically significant difference between male and female academic performance in Chemistry, according to Omwirhiren and Anderson (2016). They came to the conclusion that boys outperformed girls. Farooq and Berhanu (2011), on the other hand, discovered that female students outperformed male students. According to Nnamani and Oyibe (2016), and Jayanth (2014), gender had a significant influence on academic performance). Additionally, Maric and Sakac (2014) discovered that women perform better in university than men. MeenuDev asserts that girls performed better academically than boys (2016). The same conclusions were reached by Nnamani and Oyibe (2016). They found that girls perform better than males in social studies. Boys outperformed girls in the areas of mathematics, English, and aptitude (Eshetu, 2014). In terms of

mathematics, Manoah (2011), claimed that gender had no statistically significant impact on performance. Adigun, Onihunwa, Irunokhai, Sada, and Adesina (2015) discovered no statistical differences, but concluded that boys outperformed girls.

According to a study conducted in Nigeria to assess gender differences in academic performance of students in the Economics subject at the secondary university level, there was no statistical difference in the academic performance of boys and girls in Economics in the 2006/2007 Senior Secondary university Certificate Examination (SSCE), but there was a statistical difference in the academic performance of boys and girls in Economics from 2008 to 2010. Males generally outperformed females in economics, according to the findings (Amuda, Ali, Durkwa, 2016). The effect of gender on academic performance was still up for dispute. In Nigeria's Kashim Ibrahim College of Education, Goni, Yagana, Ali, and Bularafa (2015) discovered no statistically significant correlation between gender and academic performance using the Aptitude Test as a measure of academic performance. Wangu (2014) found that while men scored better in sciences than women, women performed better in languages.

The discussion above demonstrated how the relationship between gender and academic performance was ambiguous; although some studies found a statistically significant difference, others found no difference. Boys and girls perform differently depending on the issue, but they also had varied cognitive abilities, according to a comparison of their performance.

2.3.1.6. Student's Age and Academic Performance

Several demographic characteristics had been used to predict academic performance (Jabor, Machtmes, Kungu, & Buntat, 2011), but the impact of age on academic performance was the focus of this section. Age had a mixed effect on academic success. Ali (2013), for example, discovered

that age had a considerable impact on academic performance. Using mathematics as a measure of academic performance, Jabor (2011), came to the same conclusion. Similarly, Abubakar and Oguguo (2011) discovered that age had a considerable favourable impact on academic performance in Mathematics and Science, but the relationship was weak. Age was found to be a predictor of students' success in an online and face-to-face algebra class, according to Amro, Munday, and Kupczynski (2015).

Furthermore, Ezenwafor and Obi (2015) examined the impact of age and gender on academic performance among Nigerian Vocational and Technical Education students. Age had a major impact on academic performance, according to their findings. Because they observed a weak beneficial impact of age on academic performance, Naderi, Abdullah, Aizan, Sharir, and Kumar (2009) proposed that further research be conducted to incorporate other aspects that determined academic performance. Amuda, Bulus, and Joseph (2016), on the other hand, found that age had no bearing on academic performance. According to Voyled (2011), a student's age had little influence on his or her reading skills, but it does in mathematics.

2.3.1.7. University Factors Affecting Students' Academic Performance

University-based factors were elements that influence academic success within the university. Tuitock, Yambo, and Adhanja (2015) discovered that modern laboratories and text books were the most important university characteristics that influenced academic success in Kenyan public universities. Nambuya (2013) found that the availability of physical resources such as libraries, textbooks, adequate classrooms, and a large playing field affected children's academic performance in the same country.

Tety (2016), found that Tanzanian students' academic performance was influenced by the course materials. According to Awolaju (2016), Olayinka (2016), and Adipo (2016), students in Nigeria who were taught with instructional resources do better than students who are taught without instructional materials (2015). Krukru (2015), found that academic performance in Nigeria is significantly influenced by the instructional materials. He contended that using teaching aids facilitates the delivery of lessons and enhances both teaching and learning. The use of instructional resources helps students comprehend a topic in a subject more fully. Therefore, students who got teaching using instructional materials performed better than those who receive instruction without them (Adalikwu & Lorkpilgh, 2013).

Additionally, it had been found that a university's location significantly affected its students' academic performance. Mhiliwa (2015), asserted that a student's academic performance was impacted by the distance between their house and the university. He stressed that the farther a student had to travel to go to school from home, the hungrier and more worn out they become, which negatively affected their academic performance. He argued that students would continue to perform poorly if community universities were not offered in their area. According to Ellah and Ita (2017), students in urban areas performed better in English than students in rural ones. This suggested that students' English language proficiency was influenced by the university's location. Yusuf and Adigun (2010), on the other hand, discovered that there was no statistically significant link between university location and academic performance.

Institutions that had reasonable rules and regulations, fair penalties, and good enforcement of the rules and regulations governing students do better than universities that had less reasonable rules and regulations (Mussa, 2015). According to Ehiane (2014), effective university discipline should be used to manage students' behaviour because it had a direct impact on their academic

performance. Simba, Agak, and Kabuka claim that discipline had a strong link to academic performance (2016). They asserted that raising student discipline levels would have boosted academic performance.

Furthermore, class size or the student-to-lecturer ratio had been identified as a university component that influences academic success. According to Ajani and Akinyele (2014), there was a link between the lecturer-to-student ratio and a student's mathematics performance. According to Zyngier (2014), reduced class sizes paired with excellent teaching had a beneficial impact on academic performance. Bakasa (2011) discovered that when university characteristics like good teaching are paired with class size, academic performance improves. However, Owoeye and Olatunde (2011) discovered that there was no statistical difference in academic performance between urban and rural university classes.

There was a statistically significant difference in university amenities between private and public universities, according to Sabitu, Babatunde, and Oluwole (2012), but no statistical difference in academic performance on the other hand, Owoeye and Yara (2011) underlined that university amenities were the most significant factor in determining academic performance.

Lawrence and Vimala (2012) concluded that there was no statistically significant association between university environment and academic performance, however other studies contradicted this conclusion. For instance, Odeh, Oguche, and Dondo (2015) found that the campus environment had a significant impact on academic performance. The university setting and academic performance were found to be statistically significantly correlated, according to Duruji, Azuh, and Oviasogle (2014).

Academic performance was influenced by a variety of university-related factors, as evidenced by the studies mentioned above. However, it had been proven that important university qualities, such as class size, discipline, effective teaching, and the university environment, had a direct impact on academic performance.

2.3.2. Functions of Entrepreneurship in Economic Growth and Development

The connection between entrepreneurship and economic growth was crucial. Entrepreneurial activities had been discovered to have a positive impact on a nation's economy as well as the people's quality of life (Adejumo, 2000). Studies had shown that it has a positive relationship with economic growth, job creation, and the empowerment of the disadvantaged population, which includes women and the poor (Thomas and Mueller, 2000; Reynolds, 1987; Shapero, 1981). By creating small to medium sized firms that contributed economically to their owners, collectives, and society, entrepreneurship improves the living standard of developing countries (Cahna, 2008; Aygari, Beck, and Demirguc-Kunt 2003). "In the theory of Economic Progress," Martin Career (2002) noted, "Schumpeter identified the duty of entrepreneurs as the primary cause of economic development. Entrepreneurs were crucial because they have a substantial impact on the global economy, according to Wickham (2004). As a result of its importance in the economic development process, entrepreneurship had become a significant idea in social and human development discourse; it was regarded as a factor of economic and human development (Abubakar, 2010)

"At the heart of national development" was entrepreneurship (Porter, 1990). Many connections had been proposed in relation to the role of entrepreneurship in fostering economic growth. It is critical for implementing innovations and increasing competition. Most businesses today evolved out of the efforts of one man with a passion, an effort of one man who wanted to make money and

who wants to innovate or produce a new product. According to Schumpeter (2002), the entrepreneur had a considerable impact on capital and output growth in an economy. The entrepreneur's level of performance influences whether capital grows quickly or slowly, and whether the growth involves innovation, such as the development of new products and production procedures. The calibre of entrepreneurs in different countries accounts for a major part of the disparity in economic growth rates. Without the entrepreneur who arranges them for productive projects, the production components of land, labour, and capital are said to remain inactive or lazy (Ebiringa, 2012).

According to Ogbonifoh (1999), entrepreneurship was a critical component of any country's economic growth and development. Because entrepreneurs were born as well as made, it was true that a nation's (country's) growth is dependent on whether it had entrepreneurs and encourages them, and entrepreneurship success was largely dependent on whether human capital was deliberately harnessed and nurtured to become entrepreneurial successful.

Small firms formed by entrepreneurial oriented individuals, many of whom go on to create large businesses, were a significant driver of any economy; they create wealth and a large percentage of jobs. People who had been exposed to entrepreneurship had more creative flexibility. There was a larger sense of control over people's life and a higher sense of self-esteem. Many seasoned business professionals, political leaders, economists, and educators feel that cultivating a strong entrepreneurial culture would maximize individual and communal economic and social success on a local, national, and global scale. Entrepreneurship is important to any economy, just as it is to any community: entrepreneurship activity and the resulting financial gain are always beneficial to a country. If you had entrepreneurial talents, you would be able to see a true opportunity when you

see it. Small businesses use more labour per unit of capital and require less capital per unit of output than large businesses (Kuratko and Hodgetts, 1998).

Entrepreneurship's role in economic development entailed more than just raising per capita output and income; it also entailed starting and sustaining changes in the company and societal structures. This shift was accompanied by increased output and growth, allowing more wealth to be distributed among the various participants. One view of economic growth portrays innovation as critical not just for developing new products or services for the market, but also for generating investor interest in new initiatives (Duru, 2011).

Entrepreneurship had long been acknowledged as a key component of how businesses and economies operate (Dickson et al, 2008). It aided in the creation of new jobs, the creation of wealth, the decrease of poverty, and the generation of revenue for both the government and individuals in unfathomable ways. In 1934, Joseph Schumpeter claimed that entrepreneurship was critical to economic growth and progress (Garba, 2010). The economist view of the entrepreneur was examined by Hamilton and Harper (1994), who concluded that while the economist view was necessary but not sufficient, the sociologist and psychologist view of culture and trait was completely ignored by the economist. While economic perspectives are important, they were not adequate, according to Hamilton and Harper (1994), sociology and psychologist perspectives should also be included in the axiom of entrepreneurship.

2.3.3. Problems Facing Entrepreneurs in Nigeria

According to Durowoju (2014), knowing the great potential of entrepreneurship in achieving economic and social development, which was meant to be a top priority for governments around the world. Nigeria, also known as the "Giant of Africa," is a country with the largest population

density in Africa. Africa's population, which accounted for 15% of the continent's total, was also growing producing around 11% of Africa's overall output and 16% of its foreign exchange reserves. Nigeria was still a long way from making the economic progress required to influence or affect others improve the well-being of the average Nigerian citizen in a country where more than half of the population still lives in poverty, they were among the top three countries in the world with the largest economies, and they lived on a dollar a day a large number of destitute people

There were a variety of business prospects that both the government and entrepreneurs were overlooking. Among these were organized trans-Saharan trade, solid minerals, solar energy, waste management and recycling, tourism, garment exports, medium-tech equipment, mechanized agriculture, food/materials processing, industrial chemicals and supplies. The majority of these activities were closely related to agriculture, local knowledge/skills, and trade, which were the most important activities for a typical Nigerian (Sagagi, 2005).

According to Durowoju (2014), limited financing and support, as well as insufficient infrastructure, poor security system, and a lack of training/vocational facilities, were reported to be hindering the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria. Small enterprises in Nigeria had been hampered by a lack of basic infrastructure and security. As a result, Nigeria's cost of doing business had remained exceedingly expensive due to weak road networks, inconsistent energy and water supplies. Businesses suffered from the insecurity of lives and property. Business owners in the southern region of the country, in particular, blame limited growth on high rates of robbery and theft in their areas.

According to Oshunbiyi (1989), the main challenge that most Nigerian entrepreneurs faced was a shortage of capital for new or existing businesses. Banks, particularly commercial banks, which we anticipated to provide a platform for financing the development of entrepreneurship or small

and medium-sized businesses by providing loans, in his opinion, have failed to appropriately support them. He also commented that the bank's strict collateral security requirements often result in entrepreneurs losing their chances of receiving loans because they were unable to match the bank's demand for collateral that was worth more than the amount they wish to borrow. He went on to say that banks' exorbitant interest rates on loans deter potential small and medium-sized businesses. According to Mambula (2002), seventy-two per cent of the Nigerian entrepreneurs he researched well thought-out that a shortage of finance is a big challenge in developing and running their business.

Inadequate capital, according to Makinde (2017), is one of the issues that Nigerian entrepreneurs faced. Entrepreneurs were unable to carry out all of the wonderful projects/ideas they had formed due to a lack of funding. Borrowing from banks and other financial organizations has been difficult due to the strict criteria imposed on enterprises. This has had a significant impact on the growth of the company.

Even though entrepreneurs would play the majority of the role in entrepreneurship in Nigeria, according to Akande (1994), the government must nevertheless give training programs to improve their expertise of company management. Entrepreneurs who required management assistance could seek assistance from a variety of sources, including the Small Business Administration, management consultants, business incubators, public and university libraries, and training in industrialized countries. In developed countries such as Sweden, entrepreneurship programs were free for all entrepreneurs, and even aspiring entrepreneurs were encouraged as long as they have a good business idea. In 1996, the number of entrepreneurs with a post university education increased, and around half of those who start new businesses had a post education (NUTEK).

According to Carlson (1991), small businesses had several obstacles in the marketing environment due to a lack of information about suitable marketing techniques and procedures. Carlson (1991) went on to say that variables including the owner manager's attitude and personality, as well as the intrinsic pliability and efficiency of small business management, could assisted small business marketing understanding and strengthening. Lack of marketing focus was identified by Baker (1979) and Doyle (1985) as a major cause in business failure. An entrepreneur who lacked the abilities or ideas to sell his or her business is likely to had a marketing problem.

Gwen (2003), the ability to cost-effectively advertise, as well as real selling, were two of the most pressing issues in the marketing field. Developing a market plan, identifying new opportunities, branding the firm, competition from large businesses, getting positive publicity, identifying customers, implementing marketing strategies, understanding the customer, overcoming negative perceptions, effectively networking, getting business from large corporations, getting the decision maker, and developing new products and services were just a few of the problems that an entrepreneur faces in marketing.

Most African countries' infrastructure for information and communication is inadequate, according to Cogbun and Adeya (2000). In this era of globalization and information economy, the right or ability to access information infrastructure was viewed as a critical provision for general socio-economic improvement, even though these infrastructures are displayed at varying levels in African countries.

There were numerous factors that exacerbated the entrepreneurship technology dilemma. Basic physical infrastructure required for economic development, such as good transportation and electricity supply, was in poor condition in most developing nations, creating a challenge to

entrepreneurship. Damage to equipment as a result of power surges and downtime due to absence of electric power during production hours were examples (Echezona & Monday,2011).

Technology, according to Aiyedun (2004), was a challenge in Nigerian entrepreneurs. According to Okpara and Wynn (2007), it was pitiful that internet services and contemporary information and communication technologies were still considered inaccessible to some groups of people in Nigeria. According to Aiyedun (2004), promoting entrepreneurship in a country required the government to provide efficient communication, software development, water supply, electric power supply, rural wireless telephony and software development, road networks, vocational training, water supply and boreholes, simple tools and equipment, and a good alternative energy source.

According to Ude (1999), small business owners in most developing countries struggle to master the art and science of managing their businesses, which had hampered economic growth because they devoted less time to learning managerial skills. Financial control, production, marketing, and leadership are all skills that business management demands. Entrepreneurs require management skills in order to set up and maintain their businesses, since they required a set of competences to manage the day-to-day operations. Leadership, financial control, production marketing, planning, record keeping, and other aspects of business management necessitate skilled training.

Attempts to re-engineer important areas of the Nigerian economy, particularly banking, insurance, and oil, had been made by successive governments in managing the country's economy. A change in capitalization requirements could lead to mergers [forced succession], jeopardizing the enterprise's long-term viability. Experience abounds in Nigeria, where several regimes had used state authority to foreclose renowned entrepreneurs' enterprises or develop rules aimed at damaging their operations. As a result, many analysts said that the Asian model for economic

growth should be investigated in order to address important challenges surrounding the development of entrepreneurship in Nigeria. This was in light of the success that many Asian countries have had in developing and implementing policies geared at boosting small and medium businesses at the grassroots level (Durowoju, 2014)

Some entrepreneurs failed within the first three to six years of their existence, while others struggled to survive for up to ten years. These were caused by a variety of factors, including a lack of infrastructure, irregular power supply, a conducive educational and technical environment, a lack of research and development, unfriendly fiscal policies, excessive taxes and levies rates, policy inconsistencies, high cost of funds due to bank interest rate charges, limited access to long-term funds, a lack of skill and experience required, insecurity, and competition with foreign products, limited market access, high production costs due to insufficient infrastructure, limited access to a long-term fun, low product quality output, and a lack of training or development for its staff (Echezona & Monday,2011).

2.3.4. Determinants and Prevalence of Entrepreneurial Activities in Nigeria

There were several factors influencing people especially youths in Nigeria to engage themselves in entrepreneurial activities, for instance, unemployment was evident in the system as it was revealed that a lot graduates that are unemployed invariably due to unemployment and there was high level of poverty rate in Nigeria. Unemployment and poverty represent the macro determinants of entrepreneurial activities among youths in Nigeria. There are also micro factors which are attitude to entrepreneurship, subject norm, perceived behavioural control, gender, age, ethnicity, family background, income(allowances) and course of study that influence individuals to engage in different entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria.

2.3.5. Solutions to Challenges Facing Entrepreneurs in Nigeria

One sure way to improve potential entrepreneurs' success in Nigeria was to introduce entrepreneurship opportunities, education and training in higher institutions of learning, as well as the establishment of career centres to provide counsel to growing entrepreneurs. This would ensure that young Nigerians developed a mindset of independence, creativity, and innovation, as their Swedish counterparts do. The incorporation of this principle into all institutions of learning as part of their programs and courses would be ensured if it is backed up by government legislation.

Regular training, seminars, research, and development for management of both their business and personnel, as well as extending education and training to the illiterate population, which represented a large pool within Nigeria's entrepreneurial community, will ensure that all parties involved were well prepared for maximum productivity. More business facilitation centres, such as SMEDAN, ETDP, HAS, SBA, and business incubators, such as those found in Sweden and other developed countries, will be established across the country to provide basic training and enlighten entrepreneurs on how to go about executing proposed business plans while also providing support services at various stages of the business.

Education and training support must be used to establish a solid basis for an entrepreneur's business development. Entrepreneurs should make an effort on their own to learn about the advantages of education and training in securing business success.

Creating a competitive environment where businesses thrived by encouraging and supporting business ideas among students and young university leavers through financial support and connections to already thriving business networks where their ideas could be implemented would encourage young Nigerians to come up with innovative ideas. Other incentives include affordable

basic amenities and infrastructure, modern technology machineries and equipment required for effective and efficient production, favourable policies, free or reduced customs and excise duties for local and foreign investors, favourable immigration and repatriation laws for foreign investors, strict adherence to taxes and levies, consistent supply of electricity, and encouragement.

Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), a national entity established to promote and support the growth of entrepreneurship in Nigeria, was one example of policies and structures geared at making loans and funding options available to entrepreneurs. Banks in Nigeria set aside a particular amount of their profit on an annual basis as a source of funding for businesses as a matter of policy. However, the findings of this study revealed that corruption within these organizations makes it impossible for beneficiaries who did not have personal ties to the organizations to receive the available funds. As a result, it was critical that the government create internal monitoring and control within these agencies to verify that they are operating in accordance with their mandate. Due to transportation and other constraints, SMEDAN branches were currently located in large cities, making it difficult for businesses in remote towns to gain convenient access.

As a result, establishing local branches will go a long way toward giving interested entrepreneurs a sense of connection and accessibility. Entrepreneurial partnerships, both on a local and international level, are required to increase the capital base of enterprises. Diversify chances by discovering and generating opportunities for foreign grants through the authorities or bodies set up to supervise the interests of entrepreneurs. Nigeria's government must play a key role in encouraging entrepreneurs. In order to lower loan default risk and make additional forms of help available to entrepreneurs, they must have a solid and highly effective agreement with lending institutions.

Because widespread corruption was at the root of all of the issues confronting entrepreneurs, the Nigerian government must fight corruption at all levels of the system in order to achieve long-term solutions within the various sectors responsible for supporting entrepreneurship growth and development. Expert strategies should be established to combat problems such as inflation and political instability, so that entrepreneurs were not adversely affected by these economic ills. Assuring political stability will lead to peaceful coexistence in the country, allowing the country to expand into new areas.

Regular checks on civil servants for corrupt practices will aid in the fight against corruption. Since there was a problem with corruption within regulatory organizations and agencies set up to assist entrepreneurs. With the support of representatives, these governing bodies will function as a check on the agency while also having access to higher authorities in the event of a problem of impropriety for people to do what they need to do, the government system must be extremely rigorous. Even if you do not want to, it must be done, and it must be done well without supervision.

2.4. Summary and Gaps in Literature

From the existing literature, as reviewed in this study, which focused on the relationship between entrepreneurship and academic performance of students, different point of views and studies had been critically reviewed. From the conceptual review, it had been discussed that both entrepreneur and entrepreneurship had been relatively defined differently by different authors, scholars and studies. In essence, literature had been able to establish the different definitions of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship as it differs from time to time in that the definition of entrepreneur has its root in France in the 16th and 17th centuries and evolved over time as presented by different scholars and authors. The definitions of entrepreneur presented by different authors, scholars and studies had common indices such as risk taking, opportunities, taking advantage of opportunity, managing

resources and many more. Also, there was no general definitions of entrepreneurship as presented by different scholars, authors and studies but there were common indices.

The historical template of entrepreneurial activity in the world and Nigeria had also been reviewed in different works of literature. From the studies reviewed, it had been established that entrepreneurship had started for a long period of time in the world and Nigeria in particular. It had been established the origin of entrepreneurial activity in the world is traceable to the agricultural sector and later trade by barter but was later replaced by the invention of money. The history of entrepreneurship in Nigeria had been discussed around the three major eras in the history of the country: the precolonial era, colonial era, and the postcolonial era. Literature had been able to present differences in each of this era. In Nigeria, the entrepreneurial activities started even before the colonial of the British Empire with trading of farm products among themselves. The Colonial era in Nigeria influenced the trading system and attitudes of Nigerians to entrepreneurship and replaced their positive attitude to entrepreneurship with an educational curriculum that focused on mathematics, logic and religion. It was after Nigeria independence on October 1 1960 that the Nigerian government realized the negative influence of the British educational curriculum and therefore set up programmes to once correct and encourage the Interest of Nigerians in entrepreneurial activities examples of the organizations are, National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Nigeria Industrial Development Bank (NID), Entrepreneurship Development Centre (EDC), National Open Apprenticeship Scheme (NAOS), and many more. There were also institutions that were created for raising funds for instance, People Bank of Nigeria, funds for small industries (FUSSI), Do- operatives societies. Also, Nigerian government created education system to encourage entrepreneurship, for instance, The National Policy on Education was formulated in 1977. The policy was formulated in 1977 and revised in 1981, 1988, 2004, 2007 and 2011.

The review had also projected various scholarly definitions of the concept of academic performance. The concept had presented to be pivotal not only to the students but also to the parents to know the student current state of students' academics and also in determining the failure and success of an academic institutions. In various definitions in the literature, there are similarities in the definitions presented by scholars and studies. In the literature, academic performance is evaluated by quantifiable results like homework assignments, tests, and exam scores.

Under theoretical review, there were few works of literature that utilize theory in their study. In this course of this review, two works of literature were found that employ theories to described the relationship that exists between entrepreneurship and academic performance. The first theory reviewed was a theory on the relationship between education and training and entrepreneurship the theory called human capital theory. The second theory reviewed is a theory on the role of entrepreneurial intention in determining entrepreneurship activities called Entrepreneurial event theory. The third theory reviewed in the literature is production function approach, a theory that focused on evaluating factors that influence academic performance. These theories in their approaches had been limited, and as the first theory has been criticized for presenting that only human capital only increase productivity and it was considered to be overly simple and comparing labour with capital, the second theory was also limited in that its only considered cultural and social factors that could affect interest in entrepreneurship but did not consider other micro factors such as the person's background, belief, course of study which are capable of influencing interest in entrepreneurship, lastly, the latter theory, that was production function approach was also limited in that the factors presented that were capable of influencing academic performance was not sufficient to achieve great academic performance. However, it was important to note that no

theory is holistic in nature and for these cause other theories were to be employed to supplement deficiencies in the other.

With regard to the empirical reviews in this study, literature had been able to present factors affecting students' academic performance and in the existing works of literature several factors were projected for instance, students, lecturer, university, parents, age of students and gender of students. From the existing academic literature, problems facing entrepreneurs and solutions to these problems in Nigeria had been established. These problems were distinct in their nature as some were external to and some are internal to the businesses. The existing body of knowledge had also shown the functions of entrepreneurship in Nigeria economy growth and development. The determinants of entrepreneurial engagement and the prevalence of entrepreneurial activities among youths in Nigeria had also been reviewed.

In this chapter, it was essential to note that while previous studies had done what had been reviewed, however, they were different things that have been left out of consideration. To start with the methodology of their studies, some of the existing works of literature chose inappropriate data collection methods, while some had failed to choose the appropriate research design for their studies. In some studies, it was gathered that research philosophy adopted was incompatible with the research methodology.

From the theoretical standpoint, some of the studies reviewed in this study employed theories to support their studies. However, the theories employed were not properly adopted and utilized well in their studies. This made their study a bit excluded from proper engagement of theories.

In terms of the population of study from existing academic literature, many studies had focused on entrepreneurial activities among youths in Nigeria and there had been few or no published study

that focuses on entrepreneurial activities among students and its influence on their academic performance.

More so, literature had focused more on the functions of entrepreneurship in the economy growth and development, but few works of literature had looked into the factors that encouraged entrepreneurial engagement among youths and even students and the prevalence of entrepreneurial activities among youths and students. There had been existing literature that looked into the problems facing entrepreneurs in Nigeria but few works of literature have projected the solutions to the challenges facing entrepreneurs in Nigeria. Moreover, studies had not paid due attention to the challenges facing student entrepreneurs and government or institutions programmes to encourage entrepreneurial engagement among students. Also, due attention had not been paid the relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance among students in Nigeria.

With respect to the research gaps that had characterized the existing body of knowledge, in order to fill these gaps that exist, this study investigated the relationship that exist between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance among the students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. This study investigated the problems facing student entrepreneurs and how available programmes established by the government and institutions are helpful to encourage students and overcome challenges facing entrepreneurs even as students in Obafemi Awolowo University. This study investigated factors that determine entrepreneurial activities among the undergraduate students and examine types of entrepreneurship activities that exist among the undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University. This study engaged the quantitative research philosophy. The study also employed one hundred and fifty respondents. This study also employed primary data, and ultimately, engagement of sociological theories to proffer extensive

and explicit explanations to the relationship that exists between entrepreneurship and academic performance and also projected possible relationship that existed in the future among undergraduates in Nigerian Universities.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The place of social theory in social research cannot be overemphasised in the field of Sociology and Anthropology and this is because theories are needed to understand and explain the phenomenon under study and make predictions related to the phenomenon of interest. For any social research to be recognised by the scholarship as a body of knowledge, such study must be guided by one or two theoretical traditions in the field of Sociology. This chapter was concerned with the explanation of the theoretical framework that underlies the entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. In a bid to make this study approved in the scholarship as a body of knowledge, it was necessary to position this study within an informed theoretical framework in sociology, the study utilized two theories from the field of sociology: theory of the allocation of time and theory of planned behaviour.

3.1. Theory of the Allocation of Time

It is a theory that was propounded by Gary Becker (1965) in explaining the allocation of time to household and this theory is also called the theory of time use. According to Becker's (1965) theory of time use or theory of the allocation of time, the family has a specific time endowment per time, which is used to manufacture items that are made at home. A framework for balancing time allocation with time endowment limits is provided by Becker (1965). Although this theory refers to how time is used by households, it also addresses limitations on time allocation and the opportunity cost of diverting time set aside for one activity to another. According to Gary Becker (1965), his intention was to offer "a fundamental theoretical account of choice that incorporates the cost of time on the same footing as the cost of market items." Prior economists, he observes,

frequently took into account lost wages from time spent investing in human capital as opposed to working, but "economists have not been equally savvy about other non-working uses of time."

The study by Becker (1965) is not the first to look at how time is used at home; for instance, he cites Jacob Mincer's (1962) analysis of how married women balance time spent on housework and paid employment. The idea of a domestic production function, in which acquired things are transformed into commodities like meals that produce utility, is not entirely new either. An earlier household production article he does not cite is Terence Gorman (1980), which was written in 1956 and widely circulated as a working paper for decades before it was finally published.

However, Becker created home utility by fusing the use of things and time in a novel way. Previous labour supply models treated consumption and leisure as independent items that each offered a useful service. Becker, on the other hand, emphasised the fact that there are numerous different types of time use, much like there are numerous different types of consumption goods, and that various types of time use and consumption goods combine in various ways to produce commodities, such as prepared meals, from which we derive utility. From the observation that diverse time and consumption types merge into a single-family objective function with a single overall budget restriction, he then makes a number of significant conclusions. In what was sometimes referred to as the "New Home Economics," Becker (together with Mincer) constructed the fundamental modelling framework for almost all contemporary household level evaluations of consumption and time use.

In several aspects, Becker's model is more inclusive than those now in use. He emphasises, for instance, that different periods of time (such as weekends versus weekdays) should have various shadow costs inside the family. This contrasts with the overwhelming majority of models in use today, which link each person's time to a single observable wage rate.

3.1.1. Application of Allocation of Time Theory Postulations to entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife

This theory which was propounded by Becker, 1965 was interested in the allocation of time to household and how the time is used by the household. The theory was also interested in explaining the constraints associated with time allocation and opportunity cost with using the time allocated to a particular purpose to other activities in the household. Now applying the theory to the study of interest in order to understand how time allocated to students in Obafemi Awolowo University and the constraints faced in the management of the time in a way that academic performance was not to be affected with entrepreneurial participation on campus and off campus in Ile-Ife. The amount of time spent studying was slightly lessened if the student participated in business activities. This was due to the potential for trading off some study time for work time given the daily time constraints. It was arguable that the time trade-off has a negative impact on academic performance. This theory provided a better understanding how time available to students during the weeks and weekends despite the number of classes, tests and exams they were engaging during the session and constraints students face in the management of time and how students could engage in other activities with the time available. In Obafemi Awolowo University, time allocated to each students were different due to different fields of study or courses, for instance students in natural and applied sciences (Chemistry, Microbiology, Physics, Mechanical and Chemical Engineering and others in that respect) were allocated lesser time compared to students in humanities (Economics, Sociology and Anthropology, English Language, Philosophy and others in that respect) due long hours of practical, scope necessary to cover in a semester and other things that consume their time, from this theory we could predict that most students engaged in

entrepreneurial activities are in humanities due to the time allocated to them. Also, with this study interested in the types of entrepreneurial activities, there were types of entrepreneurial activities that the time required would definitely allow both natural and social sciences students to engage.

3.2. Theory of Planned Behaviour

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) was renamed the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) in 1980 in order to predict a person's intention to engage in a behaviour at a certain time and location. According to Ajzen's (1991) theory of planned behaviour (TPB), three variables; attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control have an impact on purpose. These elements influence the intention and subsequently the participation in a specific behaviour. The degree to which a person has a favourable or unfavourable evaluation of the behaviour in question is characterised as their attitude. It gauges how much importance a person accords a particular behaviour type. On the other side, subjective norm describes social pressure or influence from one's parents, classmates, and other respected relatives to participate in or refrain from an act or behaviour. The ability to do the behaviour and the availability of resources are both aspects of perceived behavioural control that are determined by the individual.

Depending on the degree to which a behaviour is truly controlled by the individual and the degree to which perceived behavioural control is an accurate indicator of actual behavioural control, external influences may also directly force or prevent behaviours, regardless of the intention. The hypothesis was developed to describe all actions that people can exercise self-control over. This model's most important element is behavioural intent, which is impacted by attitudes toward the likelihood that a behaviour will result in the desired outcome and a subjective assessment of the risks and advantages of that outcome.

Figure 1. The Theory of Planned Behaviour model adapted from Ajzen 2005.

3.2.1. Application of Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) Analysis to entrepreneurship and academic performance among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife

This theory propounded by Ajzen, 1997 provided better understanding why students engage in entrepreneurial activities, he identified three variables; attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control. For instance, undergraduate students engage in entrepreneurial activities because of their attitudes that is the desire to be one's own boss for example due to the high rate of unemployment in Nigeria, there have been emergence of young entrepreneurs in order to reduce the level of poverty due to unemployment and many prefer to be self-employed because they believe that to be wealthy in Nigeria is to have one's business and not living based on salary. According to research on the "State of Entrepreneurship in Nigeria 2021," 43 and 67 per cent of entrepreneurs in the nation are women and young people with ages ranging from 18 to 35, respectively (Onwuamaeze, 2022).

Also, Ajzen also identified subjective norm as a variable that can influence students' participation in entrepreneurial activities, for instance, students that receive encouragement and support from family members and relatives were more likely to engage in entrepreneurial activities than students that did not receive any support and encouragement for example to start any business there would be a need for fund to start up the business on campus because there would be a need for publicity for the business which will involve payment and other things needed to run the business which any student cannot afford unless he/she receive support from home.

Lastly, Ajzen identified that perceived behavioural control influences students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities for instance, students engage in entrepreneurial activities because of their ability to multitask and combine both business and academics.

The TPB incorporates elements from several theories of entrepreneurial intention and is the most recent behavioural theory in the literature. For instance, Adnan (2012) found that attitude and perceived behavioural control are important predictors of entrepreneurial intention with a significant positive effect when looking at undergraduate students' replies to the topic of entrepreneurial interest.

3.3. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework showed the relationship between two variables that is the relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance of undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife that is how entrepreneurial activities play role in students' academic performance and how student's academic performance play role in student intentions to engage in any type entrepreneurial activities on campus.

CHAPTER FOUR

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodology that was employed in obtaining data to explain the relationship between entrepreneurship activities and academic performance of students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. It covered the research design and the study location, target population and the sample. Also, the chapter discussed the method and technique that was utilised for the sampling, data collection, the research instrument and its validity and reliability test. The procedure for the data analysis was also explicitly stated in the chapter.

4.1. Research Design

This study sought to explain the relationship between students' entrepreneurial activities and academic performance in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Nigeria; hence, this study employed a cross-sectional explanatory survey research design. The rationale behind this choice of research design was to bring a better understanding of the relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance among students in Obafemi Awolowo University and to establish the causal relationship between the variables. The rationale behind the adoption of the design was based on the nature of the study and data collection that was done once and for all.

4.2. Study Location

The study was conducted in one of the first-generation universities and leading higher citadels of learning in Nigeria known as the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, formerly named, the University of Ife. It was established during the Western Regional government led by Ladoke Akintola in the year 1962. The institution is located in Ile Ife in Osun State, Southwestern part of

Nigeria. It occupies about 11, 000 hectares expanse of land and ranks second university with the largest expanse of land.

Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, is made up of about 32,480 students and over 12,000 staff (OAU official website, 2023). There are faculties in the institution which are; Basics Medical Sciences, Pharmacy, Social Sciences, Agriculture, Science, Technology, Dentistry, Education, Law, Administration, Art, Environmental Design Management and Clinical Sciences. His Royal Highness, Alhaji (Dr) Yahaya Abubakar, (CFR), is the Chancellor of Obafemi Awolowo University. Accordingly, Professor Adebayo Simeon Bamire is the Vice-Chancellor.

Figure 1: The Google map is showing the location of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Nigeria. (Source: Google Maps, 2022)

4.3. Population of the Study

The population that was employed for this study were the undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University that were entrepreneurs from different faculties.

4.4. Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

This study drawn 150 students using Fisher method ($n = Z^2 * P * q / d^2$) for unknown population where the $Z=1.96$, $d=0.05$, $q= 1-p$ and $p=0.10956$. Since 95% confidence level and a margin of error of 5% is needed in social science, the study used the Fisher's exact formula to calculate the sample size. These students were into different entrepreneurial activities in Obafemi Awolowo University in Ile Ife from the population of students. Since there was no registered association for students who engage in entrepreneurial activities for now, sampling involved snowballing approach.

4.5. Sampling Procedures

The samples were drawn from the research population using purposive sampling technique at first and other participants were selected using snowball sampling technique. This referral continued until the required number of participants in the research was reached.

4.6. Method of Data Collection

In a quest to obtain information on the relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academics performance among students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, this study employed quantitative data collection method.

4.7. Research Instrument

This study employed a questionnaire survey in a bid to get the data from the research participants. The questionnaire contained close-ended questions. The questionnaire survey covered the socio-demographic details of the participants, and each of the research questions that had been identified in the introductory part of the research study employed to phrase the questions asked in other sections of the questionnaire. The rationale for the utilisation of the questionnaire was based on

the need to cover enough data from the research participants and to ensure that the data collected was the true representation of the whole population, that is the undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife.

4.8. Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The items of the questionnaire were prepared after a thorough review of relevant literature in the study and copies of it were given to the project supervisor who studied them and made necessary corrections and confirmed them as being relevant to the study. The corrections were incorporated in the final draft of the questionnaire in order to ensure its validity.

A pilot test was conducted using few selected subjects. The essence of the test of the questionnaire was to see whether the items were clear enough, easily understood and if there was need to include more items in certain areas or whether there were some items to which they could not like to respond to. The data from the questionnaire were analysed and this was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and to determine whether the methods of data analysis proposed for the main study were workable.

In all, one hundred and fifty (150) copies of the questionnaires were distributed to entrepreneurs that are students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife. The procedure for filling the questionnaire was thoroughly explained to them.

4.9. Data Collection Procedure

The collection of the data used close-ended questionnaire, due to the nature of the study. The questionnaire was administered using google form at the lecture theatres, library, car packs, halls of residence both on campus and off-campus, religious centres on campus like Mosque and Christian fellowship centres and other space where students involved in entrepreneurial activities

could be found. Furthermore, there was follow-up to ensure that all the questionnaire are filled by the participants.

In conclusion, the data that was collected was treated with much care putting into consideration the ethics that guide social enquiry. Data obtained was taken to the next process of research, which is data analysis.

4.10. Method of Data Analysis

This study utilised an analytical data package called the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for the analysis of the quantitative data.

4.11. Ethical Considerations

In sociological enterprise, ethical considerations are important to be considered while conducting any research and for the research to be approved and acceptable in the scholarship. This study which was interested in the relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance of the students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife was not excluded from the ethical guidelines that govern social enquiry as there are rules and regulations that guide any sociological research.

In the view of this, this study, in a quest to align with globally accepted practices of social research, ensured that the consent of every participant in this study was properly sought. In order to achieve this, the purpose of this study was related to the research participants and a consent form was attached to the questionnaire that was administered by the respondents. The content form was presented to the participants before the attempt to fill the questionnaire. In case, any participant refuses to give his/her consent then the questionnaire was administered.

Furthermore, confidentiality and anonymity of the responses of the participants was guaranteed. On the questionnaire, the confidentiality and anonymity assurance information came before the first section of the questions on the questionnaire, which entailed the socio-demographical information of the participants. Importantly, harm against participants was prevented in the course of the research because the researcher was interested in physical and emotional wellbeing of the research participants.

Importantly, this research ensured that the autonomy of the respondents was respected. In the course of gathering data from the participants, this study was not in any way force its will on the respondents.

CHAPTER FIVE

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter, presented the analysis, interpretation and discussion of the data collected from the field. The analysis was done with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 2.0). The last segment of this chapter was focused on the discussion of the findings from the 150 participants covered in this study. The discussion of the findings was to situate findings in the existing literature and theories.

Table 5.1: Socio-demographic Background of the Respondents

VARIABLES	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION	PER CENTAGE (%)
Sex	Male	55	36.7
	Female	95	63.3
Age (Year)	18-21	32	21.4
	22-25	100	66.7
	26-29	15	10
	30-33	3	2.1
Level	200	30	20.0
	300	35	23.3
	400	81	54
	500	4	2.7
Faculty	Social Sciences	93	61
	Administration	10	7.4
	Education	7	4.1
	Environmental Design Management	5	3.4
	Technology	6	4.2
	Arts	11	7.6
	Science	5	3.4
	Pharmacy	3	2.0
	Health Sciences	4	2.8
	Agriculture	5	3.5
	Law	1	0.7
Religion	Christianity	137	91.3
	Islam	13	8.7

From the table 5.1. 36.7% of the respondents were males, while the female accounted for 63.3% of the sample. This shows that females were more interested in entrepreneurial activities than males due to the fact that entrepreneurship requires skills that females naturally possess.

Also, 20% of the respondents were in 200 level, 23.3% were in 300, 26% were 400 level. Lastly, 2.7% of them indicated that they were in 500 level. The variation in distribution in the levels was due to availability and accessibility. The absence of sampling frame has made it difficult to equally select the respondents.

On age distribution 21.4% of the respondents were within the age of 18 and 21 years; 66.7% were between 22 and 25 years and 10% were within the ages 26 and 29 years Lastly, 2.1% were within the age range of 30-33 years. This shows that the age distribution of the respondents was from between 18 and 33 years. It can be concluded that the age distribution for most students that are into entrepreneurial activities is between 22 and 25 years of age.

On the Faculty of the respondents, 7.4% of the sample were from the Faculty of administration, 11% from the Faculty of Art, 5% of the sample were from the faculty of Agricultural Sciences, 4% of the sample were from the College of Health Sciences, 7% of the sample revealed from the Faculty of Education, 5% of the sample were from the Faculty of Environmental Design and Management, 1% of the sample are from the Faculty of Law, Faculty of Technology accounted for the 6% of the sample, 5% from the Faculty of Sciences, 93% from the Faculty of Social Sciences and 3% from the Faculty of Pharmacy. The variation in the distribution among faculties is not deliberate on the part of the researcher and this is due to the accessibility and availability of the respondents that make the population of the social sciences more than other faculties and also because of the fact that the researcher is in the faculty itself.

From the table, 91.3% of the sample practise Christianity, and 8.7% practise Islam. The analysis shows that those that practices Christianity are more dominant in this study, the rationale for the domination of the Christians is traceable to the techniques used in collecting the data. This difference however, does not have effect on the findings of this study.

Table 5.2: Factors That Determine Undergraduate Students' Engagement in Entrepreneurial Activities in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife

Strongly Agree = 5, Agree = 4, Neutral=3, Disagree=2 and Strongly Agree=1

VARIABLES	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION	POINTS
My desire to own a business influenced my entrepreneurial engagement	Strongly Agree	75	375
	Agree	48	192
	Neutral	17	51
	Disagree	10	20
	Strongly Disagree	0	0
I engage in entrepreneurship because of the influence family members or close friends who are entrepreneurs	Strongly Agree	16	80
	Agree	34	136
	Neutral	37	111
	Disagree	56	112
	Strongly Disagree	7	7
My decision for entrepreneurship is a function of entrepreneurship courses or classes at Obafemi Awolowo University	Strongly Agree	7	35
	Agree	10	40
	Neutral	25	75
	Disagree	74	148
	Strongly Disagree	34	34
It is because I participate in any entrepreneurship programmes or activities at Obafemi Awolowo University	Strongly Agree	5	25
	Agree	10	40
	Neutral	25	75
	Disagree	87	174
	Strongly Disagree	23	23
I take to entrepreneurship because of my worry or anxiety about my ability to find and maintain employment in Nigeria in the future	Strongly Agree	36	180
	Agree	56	224
	Neutral	31	93
	Disagree	23	46
	Strongly Disagree	4	4
I am into entrepreneurship because the government support can encourage entrepreneurship in Nigeria	Strongly Agree	9	45
	Agree	13	52
	Neutral	41	123
	Disagree	69	138
	Strongly Disagree	18	18
It is because of my access to financial resources to start my own business or venture	Strongly Agree	23	115
	Agree	44	176
	Neutral	35	105
	Disagree	41	82
	Strongly Disagree	7	7
My academic programme has influenced my decision to become an entrepreneur	Strongly Agree	25	125
	Agree	45	180
	Neutral	39	117
	Disagree	27	54
	Strongly Disagree	14	14

In this table, the factors that determine students' entrepreneurial activities were probed, it can be concluded based on the points that students' desire to own a business played a vital in their involvement in entrepreneurial activities. More so, it cannot really be certain that family members or close friends that are entrepreneurs had a major impact in students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities based on the points. Based on the points in the table, entrepreneurship courses or classes at OAU, Ile Ife have no effect on students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities. Participation of students in any entrepreneurial activities or programmes at OAU, Ile Ife have no effect on students' entrepreneurial activities. On whether, anxiety about students' abilities to find and maintain employment in Nigeria in the future, the points showed that it truly had an impact on students' entrepreneurial activities that is most students are into entrepreneurship engagements because of their anxieties about their employment statuses in the future. Also, government support did not have any impact on students' entrepreneurial activities based on the points in the table. The table revealed that access to financial resources have considerable impact on students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities. Lastly, academic programme had a major impact on students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities based on the points in the table that is students consider the prospects on their academic programmes before engaging in entrepreneurial activities.

Table 5.3: Possible Effects of Entrepreneurial Activities Among Undergraduate Students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife

VARIABLES	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION	PER CENTAGE (%)
How has your experience as an entrepreneur affected your academic performance?	Positively	62	41.3
	Negatively	17	11.3
	No effect	71	47.3
What was the range of your current CGPA before engaging in entrepreneurial activities?	4.50-5.00	25	16.7
	3.50-4.49	73	48.7
	2.40-3.49	45	30.0
	1.50-2.39	7	4.7
	1.00-1.49	0	0
What is the range of your current CGPA/GP after engaging in entrepreneurial activities?	4.50-5.00	20	13.3
	3.50-4.49	79	52.7
	2.40-3.49	46	30.7
	1.50-2.39	5	3.3
	1.00-1.49	0	0
How will your experience as an entrepreneur affect your career prospects after graduation?	Positively	131	87.3
	Negatively	4	2.7
	No effect	15	10.0
How has your entrepreneurship engagement affected your confidence and self-esteem?	Positively	133	88.7
	Negatively	4	2.7
	No effect	13	8.7
Have you gained any new skills or knowledge as a result of your entrepreneurship engagement?	Yes	145	96.7
	No	5	3.3
Do you believe that entrepreneurship can be a viable career option for undergraduate students?	Yes	146	97.3
	No	4	2.7
Do you plan to continue your entrepreneurship engagement after graduation?	Yes	144	96.0
	No	6	4.0
Do your entrepreneurial activities affect your classes' attendance?	Yes	52	34.7
	No	98	65.3

Source: Field Survey, 2023

In this table, possible effects of entrepreneurial activities among undergraduate students in OAU, Ile Ife were probed. It cannot be ascertained that students' entrepreneurship experiences affected their academic performance because based on the results, most students that were in first and second class before engaging in entrepreneurial activities were still in first and second class even after they started entrepreneurial activities which is affirming that academic performance was not affected with students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities which is in accordance with previous researches. The results further showed that students career prospects have been affected positively and their self-esteem and confidence have been affected positively due to their entrepreneurial activities. The results showed that students gained new skills as a result of their entrepreneurial activities and students believed in entrepreneurship as a viable career option for undergraduate students like themselves that is other students should consider entrepreneurship as a possible option in their choice of career. Also, it can be concluded that students are likely to venture into entrepreneurial activities after graduation and become full-time entrepreneurs. Lastly, the results showed that entrepreneurial activities did not affect students' classes attendances which also reflected in their academic performance as most students are still in first and second class even after engaging entrepreneurial activities.

Table 5.4: Typologies of Entrepreneurial Activities Among Undergraduate Students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife

VARIABLES	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION	PER CENTAGE (%)
Do you know any successful entrepreneurs who are currently in the industry and is a source of encouragement to you?	Yes	102	68.0
	No	48	32.0
What is your level of involvement?	Financing the business	14	9.3
	Involve in the entire process of the business	112	74.7
	Marketing of the business	24	16.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The table showed that most students had successful entrepreneurs that they modelled their entrepreneurial activities after even after graduation at OAU, Ile Ife. Also, the table showed that students were usually involved in the entire process of business which implies students were owners of their entrepreneurial activities.

Table 5.5: Availability of Programmes/Platforms to Encourage Undergraduate Students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife

VARIABLES	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION	PER CENTAGE (%)
Are you aware of any entrepreneurship programmes or platforms available on your campus?	Yes	20	13.3
	No	130	86.7
Have you participated in any of the entrepreneurship programmes or platforms available on campus?	Yes	24	16.0
	No	124	84.0
Have you received any mentorship or coaching in entrepreneurship from the programmes or platforms available on your campus?	Yes	33	22.0
	No	117	78.0
Do you think there should be more resources available for entrepreneurs on campus?	Yes	141	94.0
	No	9	6.0
Have you ever attended any entrepreneurship events organised by the organisers of the programmes or platforms available on your campus?	Yes	64	42.7
	No	86	57.3
Would you recommend the entrepreneurship programs or platforms available on your campus to other students?	Yes	120	80.0
	No	30	20.0
Do you think the entrepreneurship programmes or platforms available on your campus contribute to the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem in your community?	Yes	106	70.7
	No	44	29.3
How effective do you think the entrepreneurship programs or platforms available on your campus are in encouraging entrepreneurship among students?	Very Effective	51	34.0
	Somewhat Effective	80	53.3
	Somewhat Ineffective	14	9.3
	Very Ineffective	5	3.3

Source: Field Survey, 2023

In this table, the results gathered in the field, showed that students were not aware of any entrepreneurship programmes or platforms which in turn affected their participation in any entrepreneurship programmes on campus as many of them had never participated in any entrepreneurship programmes. Based on the results, students had not received any mentorship programmes and they believed that more resources in form of programmes should be made available to them in order to aid their entrepreneurial activities on campus. Also, the results showed students were ready to recommend available if there be any programmes or platforms that could aid entrepreneurial activities to their colleagues on campus. Lastly, students believed that available entrepreneurship programmes would contribute to the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem because they believed that those programmes can be effective in aiding entrepreneurial activities. It can be concluded that even without available entrepreneurship programmes that can aid students, students are still doing well academically in different respects.

Table 5.6: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My desire to own a business influenced my entrepreneurial engagement"	150	2	5	4.25	.906
I engage in entrepreneurship because of the influence family members or close friends who are entrepreneurs	150	1	5	2.97	1.105
My decision for entrepreneurship is a function of entrepreneurship courses or classes at Obafemi Awolowo University	150	1	5	2.21	1.021
It is because I participate in any entrepreneurship programs or activities at Obafemi Awolowo University"	150	1	5	2.25	.912
I take to entrepreneurship because of my worry or anxiety about my ability to find and maintain employment in Nigeria in the future	150	1	5	3.65	1.088
I am into entrepreneurship because the government support can encourage entrepreneurship in Nigeria	150	1	5	2.51	1.015
It is because of my access to financial resources to start my own business or venture	150	1	5	3.23	1.149

From the table, the mean score showed that desire to own a business has a significant impact on entrepreneurial engagement while influence of family member or close friends had no significant impact at all. Also, based on the mean score entrepreneurial courses at OAU and participation in

any entrepreneurship programmes had no significant impact on entrepreneurial engagement among students. Furthermore, the mean score showed that students engage in entrepreneurial activities because of their anxiety or worry about the ability to find and maintain employment in Nigeria. Lastly, based on the mean score government support had no significant impact on entrepreneurial engagement while access to financial resources to start to own business had significant impact on students. These findings showed that desire to own a business had a strong impact than other factors presented in this study.

5.7. Discussion of Findings

This study, which sought to understand the relationship entrepreneurship and academic performance of students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, covered 150 students' entrepreneurs on OAU campus. The participants were picked from 11 of 13 faculties in OAU. The participants had male and female ably represented in this study, along with diverse age grades ranging from 18 years old to 33 years old. The participants were noted to be from the two major religions in Nigeria: Christianity and Islam. Moreover, the study participants employed were undergraduates' students of OAU.

From the data gathered on the factors that determine undergraduate students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities, this study found out that students' desires to own a business have a strong influence on their entrepreneurial activities and the results showed that students who receive encouragement from family members have a higher likelihood of engagement in entrepreneurship relative to those who do not receive family support. Students who perceive that they were not be able to combine entrepreneurial activity with academic work show negative tendency of engagement in entrepreneurship.

The result also suggested that students whose parents are currently employed were more likely to engage in entrepreneurship. This was particularly for those with parents in self-employment. This suggested that family business background significantly influences students' entrepreneurial interest. These results were in agreement with the findings of Osakede (2017) who opined that the engagements of students in entrepreneurial activities were due to that their family members had a major influence on them and their desires also influence them too. From this study, it showed that students' decisions to engage in entrepreneurial activities were not due to any entrepreneurship

courses or classes on campus or due to any participation in any entrepreneurship programmes on campus.

The results showed students take to entrepreneurship due to anxiety about their ability to find and maintain employment in Nigeria due to high rate of unemployment of young graduates. In this, the study showed that government support did not have any impact on students' entrepreneurial engagements because government support will necessarily not be enough to aid them and this is evidenced in the high rate of poverty in Nigeria. Also, students access to financial resources had been a major factor that determine students' entrepreneurial activities according to the results in the survey. This study considered academic programme/course that other studies did not consider as a factor that determine entrepreneurial activities of students and the findings of this study showed that academic programmes of students influence their engagements in entrepreneurship.

The results in this study showed that engagement in business had no remarkable effect on students' academic performance as the survey showed that there was no effect students CGPA as the survey showed students CGPA before engaging in entrepreneurial activities that is most students were first- and second-class students and after engaging in entrepreneurial activities they were still in first and second class. These results were in agreement with the findings of Osakede (2017) who opined that engagement in business had no remarkable negative effect on students' academic performance. The results also showed that students experiences as entrepreneurs have affected their career prospects positively that is most students were likely to become self-employed and entrepreneurs after graduation. The study also showed that students' confidence had been developed positively as they engage in entrepreneurial activities. The results in the study showed that students gained new skills as they engage in entrepreneurial activities on campus.

The findings on the typologies of entrepreneurial activities among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, the results showed that students have role models that influenced their choice of entrepreneurial activities that they engage in. The results on students' involvement in entrepreneurship activities showed how they were involved in the entire process of the business.

In conclusion, with the findings from this study, it showed that students were not aware of any entrepreneurship programmes or platforms and as a result had not participated in any in entrepreneurship programmes or platforms. The results showed that students had not received any mentorship in entrepreneurship that can aid in entrepreneurial activities. The findings showed that students were willing to recommend entrepreneurship programmes to other students on campus.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary, conclusion, recommendations, contribution to knowledge and suggestion for further studies.

6.1. Summary of the Study

The study investigated the relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife. This study was divided into six Chapters that deal with different sections. The first chapter contained the background of the study, where the motivation of this researcher for this study was presented. Also contained in the chapter were the statement of the research problem, the research questions and the specific objectives. More so, the chapter contained the significance of the study, its scope and the definitions of the key concepts.

The second chapter was on the review of the relevant works. The chapter was divided into three sections, on conceptual classifications namely; entrepreneurship and academic performance. The second section covered the related theories: production function approach and human capital theory and the third section was the empirical review of studies related to factors determining students' entrepreneurial activities and contribution of entrepreneurship to the economic development in Nigeria. The reviewed works were highlighted in the concluding part of the chapter.

The third chapter presented the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study. The sociological theories used to establish the relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance in this study were theory of the allocation of time and theory of planned

behaviour. The study under the conceptual framework presented the nature of the relationship that existed between the two variables: entrepreneurial activities as an independent variable and academic performance as a dependent variable.

Chapter four covered the methodology. Discussed in the chapter were the research design, description of the study location, population and the sample, sampling techniques, description of tool for data collection and data analysis.

In chapter five, the data presentation, interpretation, analysis and discussion of findings was done. The findings of this study show family members, desire and academic programmes had major influence on students' interest in entrepreneurial activities on campus. The study has also shown that there was no significant relationship between entrepreneurial activities and academic performance as revealed in many researches. The study has also shown that there was no available entrepreneurship programmes or platforms to students on campus.

6.2. Conclusion

This study, concluded that desire to own a business, members of family, academic programmes of students had major influence on students' engagement in involvement of entrepreneurship in OAU, Ile Ife. Also, entrepreneurial activities had no remarkable negative impact on students' academic performance.

6.3. Contributions to the Body of Knowledge

This study has been able to expand the boundaries of knowledge to add to factors that determine students' engagement in entrepreneurial activities in the tertiary institution. These were typologies of entrepreneurial activities of students and available entrepreneurship programmes or platforms provided by the organisations that have aided students that are entrepreneurs.

6.4. Limitations of the Study

This study was not able to probe typologies of entrepreneurial activities among students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife. These limitations include a potentially small sample size, due to limited time and resources. Despite these limitations, the study provided useful insights into the relationship between entrepreneurship among students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

6.5. Suggestion for Further Studies

This study would, however suggest further studies on this topic to employ a mixed research method. Further studies might also need to probe the reasons the possible effects of entrepreneurial activities on academic performance and typologies of entrepreneurial activities among students. Further research might also need to research this topic by using a larger sample in order to aid generalisation.

6.6. Recommendations

From the findings the following recommendations become pertinent.

Nigerian Universities should further provide entrepreneurship programmes or platform that will encourage entrepreneurial activities.

Government actions to promote entrepreneurship in tertiary institutions should be further intensified in order to achieve required aim of reducing unemployment for the teeming Nigerian graduate population.

Focus areas in curricular course work for entrepreneurship in Nigerian universities should consider modules that influence the student's attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control.

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APPENDIX
SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

I am Olaoye Timilehin Samuel, a final year student of the Department of Sociology and Anthropology working on Entrepreneurship and Academic Performance among Undergraduate Students in Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), ILE IFE, in partial fulfillment of my bachelor degree in Sociology and Anthropology. I hereby assure you that the study is solely for academic purpose, and respondents would be treated with utmost confidentiality. Please, answer all the questions appropriately and truthfully. Thanks

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC BACKGROUND OF RESPONDENTS

1	Sex	Male () Female ()
2	Faculty	
3	Level	100 () 200() 300() 400() 500() 600()
4	Age (as at last birthday)	
5	Religion	Christianity () Islam () Others (specify)_____

SECTION B: FACTORS THAT DETERMINE UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT IN ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES IN OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE IFE

		Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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6	My desire to own a business influenced my entrepreneurial engagement					
7	I engage in entrepreneurship because of the influence family members or close friends who are entrepreneurs					
8	My decision for entrepreneurship is a function of entrepreneurship courses or classes at Obafemi Awolowo University					
9	It is because I participate in any entrepreneurship programs or activities at Obafemi Awolowo University					
10	I take to entrepreneurship because of my worry or anxiety about my ability to find and maintain employment in Nigeria in the future					
11	I am into entrepreneurship because the government support can encourage entrepreneurship in Nigeria					
12	It is because of my access to financial resources to start my own business or venture					
13	My academic programme has influenced my decision to become an entrepreneur					

SECTION C: POSSIBLE EFFECTS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN OBAFEMI AWOLowo UNIVERSITY, ILE IFE

14	How has your experience as an entrepreneur affected your academic performance?	Positively () Negatively () No effect ()
15	What was the range of your current CGPA before engaging in entrepreneurial activities?	4.50-5.00 () 3.50-4.49 () 2.40-3.49 () 1.50-2.39 () 1.00-1.49 ()
16	What is the range of your current CGPA after engaging in entrepreneurial activities?	4.50-5.00 () 3.50-4.49 () 2.40-3.49 () 1.50-2.39 () 1.00-1.49 ()
17	How will your experience as an entrepreneur affect your career prospects after graduation?	Positively () Negatively () No effect ()
18	How has your entrepreneurship engagement affected your confidence and self-esteem?	Positively () Negatively () No effect ()

		Yes	No
19	Have you gained any new skills or knowledge as a result of your entrepreneurship engagement?		
20	How has your entrepreneurship engagement affected your confidence and self-esteem?		

21	Do you believe that entrepreneurship can be a viable career option for undergraduate students?		
22	Do you plan to continue your entrepreneurship engagement after graduation?		
23	Do your entrepreneurial activities affect your classes' attendance?		

SECTION D: TYPOLOGIES OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN OBAFEMI AWOLowo UNIVERSITY, ILE IFE

		Yes	No
24	Do you know any successful entrepreneurs who are currently in the industry and is a source of encouragement to you?		

25. What is your level of involvement? A. Financing the business () B. Involve in the entire process of the business () C. Marketing of the business ()

26. If you answered "Yes" to the question 24, please specify the name and type of industry of the successful entrepreneur. _____

SECTION E: AVAILABILITY OF PROGRAMMES/PLATFORMS TO ENCOURAGE UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN OBAFEMI AWOLowo UNIVERSITY, ILE IFE

		Yes	No
27	Are you aware of any entrepreneurship programmes or platforms available on your campus?		
28	Have you participated in any of the entrepreneurship programmes or platforms available on campus?		
29	Have you received any mentorship or coaching in entrepreneurship from the programmes or platforms available on your campus?		
30	Do you think there should be more resources available for entrepreneurs on campus?		

31	Have you ever attended any entrepreneurship events organised by the organisers of the programmes or platforms available on your campus?		
32	Would you recommend the entrepreneurship programs or platforms available on your campus to other students?		
33	Do you think the entrepreneurship programmes or platforms available on your campus contribute to the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem in your community?		

34	How effective do you think the entrepreneurship programmes or platforms available on your campus are in encouraging entrepreneurship among students?	Very effective () Somewhat effective () Somewhat ineffective () Very ineffective ()
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35. If you answered "Yes" to the question 1, please specify the name of the programme or platform you are aware of. _____

Thank you for your help in filling this questionnaire.